

Antioxidant activity of various fractions of humic substances in cosmetic compositions

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Over the past two decades, interest in humic substances has expanded significantly and gone beyond the traditional study of soil organic matter; there is a demand for new humic-based products. This situation poses a challenge for science aimed at finding new areas of their application. For example, the use of humic substances in the cosmetic industry. Of particular interest is the use of humic substances as antioxidants, because scientists have opened a long time ago the presence of antioxidant properties in these compounds due to their structural features (the presence of a large number of quinoid, hydroxyl and carboxyl groups) [1].

The aim of this work was the study of antioxidant properties of humic substances in pure form and in cosmetic compositions. The object of the study was the fractions of humic and fulvic acids isolated from lowland peat.

To obtain humic substances, the alkaline extraction method was used. Humic acids were isolated by acidifying a sodium humate solution with a hydrochloric acid solution, and fulvic acids were isolated from the acidic filtrate after precipitation of humic acids, using adsorption of organic components on BAU-A carbon.

One of the possible parameters characterizing antioxidant capacity is the reducing capacity, defined as the amount of oxidizer reduced during interaction with a substance, normalized to its mass. To establish this parameter a spectrophotometric technique was used, which is based on the reaction of Fe (III) reduction to Fe (II) in the presence of humic substances. It was found that humic acids have the highest reducing capacity (more than the antioxidant comparison has) among humic substances, which may indicate greater antioxidant activity.

Emulsions were chosen as cosmetic compositions to introduce of antioxidants, since they are one of the most common cosmetic forms. In cosmetic emulsion compositions, humic acids also had greater antioxidant activity compared to fulvic acids and humic-fulvic complex.

Thus, humic substances are a promising antioxidant component for introduction into cosmetic emulsion forms. The obtained data can serve as a basis for the development of cosmetics and medicines.

References

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